

Crop management

Effect of traditional and improved nursery methods on seedling growth and rice yield

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In the Konkan region of Maharashtra, rice seedlings traditionally are raised on a flat nursery bed on which a large quantity of cow dung, twigs of trees (*Terminalia* spp.), dry grass, and dry leaves of forest trees have been burned. To further increase soil temperature, burning is slowed by spreading a thin layer of fine soil on top of the organic matter.

Each year, branches of forest trees and bushes are cut to collect organic matter. That eventually depletes the forests and degrades the soils. In the summer, skeletons of *Terminalia* trees and burned patches of fields are common sights.

Weed control seems to be the only objective of this traditional method. Although the seedlings raised are vigorous, long-term detrimental effects do not warrant the short-term advantages.

We evaluated the traditional method against improved methods of raising seedlings in two consecutive experiments during 1988 wet season. Treatments included preburning of nursery bed and raised and flat nursery beds with various mechanical and herbicidal weed control treatments (see table).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil of the experimental plot was lateritic having 152.5, 6.9, and 248.9 kg available N, P, K/ha. Plot sizes were 6 × 1 m for the nursery and 4.6 × 4.2 m for transplanting. Nursery area burning was done in May 1988 and Ratnagiri 24 was planted in Jun 1988. Preemergence herbicides were applied on wet soil.

Seedlings from the set of nursery treatments were transplanted in a different field in a randomized block design with three replications. Recommended plant population (20 × 15 cm), fertilizers (100 kg N, 22 kg P/ha), and plant protection measures were applied uniformly to all treatments.

Seedling height and dry matter in the traditional rice nursery were more than twice that in the other nursery treatments (see table). This could be attributed to increased availability of N (10%), P (39%), and K (100%). Also, all weeds were eliminated.

However, the pretransplanting differences did not significantly affect crop yields. Seedlings from the traditional nursery were not superior to seedlings from improved nurseries.

Thus, the traditional method benefits only the nursery and should be discouraged to save valuable organic matter and vegetation. Instead, herbicides should be used to control weeds in the nursery. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Nonfluorescent *Pseudomonas* strains causing rice sterility and grain discoloration in Colombia

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Two nonfluorescent species of *Pseudomonas*, *P. avenae* and *P. glumae*, cause seedling rot, grain discoloration (GID), and sterility in rice. *P. avenae* is known to be distributed worldwide; until a recent report from Latin America, *P. glumae* was known only in Asia. Reports on the

Effect of preburning nursery bed and raised and flat bed nurseries with different weed control methods on seedling growth and transplanted rice yield.^a

Treatment	Seedling height (cm)	Dry matter/seedling (mg)	Dry weight of weeds (t/ha)	Weed control efficiency (%)	Available N (kg/ha)	Available P (kg/ha)	Exchangeable K (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Rabbing (preburning)	10.5	115.0	-	100	168.7	9.9	439.1	2.4	3.0
Raised bed + unweeded control	5.8	42.0	1.2	13.3	152.7	6.8	233.8	2.4	2.8
Raised bed + weed-free check	6.3	47.3	0.3	75.9	153.5	7.1	224.0	2.8	3.2
Flat bed + unweeded control	5.7	40.0	1.4	0.0	156.1	6.9	237.2	2.3	2.8
Flat bed + weed-free check	6.0	46.3	0.3	75.9	150.3	7.2	237.2	2.8	3.1
Raised bed + one hand weeding	5.8	49.3	0.3	76.3	153.1	7.0	240.5	2.8	3.0
Flat bed + one hand weeding	5.7	46.3	0.3	75.9	152.6	6.9	233.1	2.3	2.8
Raised bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 50 EC/ha at preemergence	5.3	34.6	0.2	85.1	146.1	7.0	238.7	2.2	2.6
Flat bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 50 EC/ha at preemergence	5.5	36.0	0.2	84.7	146.1	7.1	241.8	2.1	2.8
Raised bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 10% G/ha at preemergence	4.9	33.6	0.2	85.1	144.9	6.9	234.4	2.3	2.7
Flat bed + 3.0 kg ai butachlor 10% G/ha at preemergence	5.7	38.0	0.2	84.7	151.4	6.9	238.8	2.2	2.7
Raised bed + 1.0 kg ai oxadiazon/ha at preemergence	4.9	37.0	0.2	85.5	151.4	7.0	229.2	2.4	2.8
Flat bed + 1.0 kg ai oxadiazon/ha at preemergence	5.9	41.0	0.2	85.1	154.3	6.9	237.3	2.5	2.9
LSD (0.05)	1.1	9.9	0.1		6.5	0.6	25.4	ns	ns

^a Nursery variables measured at time of uprooting seedlings.